

A Facile Synthesis of 4-Propyl-psoralene and Angelicin Derivatives

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7-Hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (1) on allylation followed by Claisen migration of the intermediate allyloxycoumarin 2 with *N,N*-dimethylaniline gives 8-allyl- and 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-ones (3 and 4) which on oxidation with $\text{OsO}_4 - \text{KIO}_4$ and subsequent cyclodehydration with PPA yield 7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-h][1]benzopyran-5-one (7) and 5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (10), respectively. However, these allyl coumarins 3 and 4 on cyclisation with sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation with DDQ afford 2-methyl-7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-h][1]benzopyran 5-one (9) and 2-methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran 7-one (12) respectively. Similarly, 9-methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (16) and 2,9-dimethyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (18) are synthesised starting from 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (13).

THE natural occurrence¹⁻⁴, photodynamic activity^{5,6} of psoralene and angelicin derivatives and insecticidal properties⁷ of 4-propylcoumarins prompted us to devise a convenient method for the synthesis of 4-propyl angelicins and psoralenes. Different methods⁸⁻¹⁶ have been used for the synthesis of psoralene and angelicin derivatives. But no considerable efforts have so far been made for the synthesis of 4-propyl angelicins and psoralenes. In the present communication, synthesis of 4-propyl angelicin and psoralene derivatives, viz. 7, 9, 10, 12, 16 and 18 has been described.

Results and Discussion

7-Hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (1)¹⁷ on allylation with allylbromide in acetone and anhydrous potassium carbonate gave 7-allyloxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (2) which on Claisen migration with *N,N*-dimethylaniline afforded a mixture of two products, viz. 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (3) (60%) and 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (4) (10%). The 6-allyl isomer was obtained exclusively (60%) by allylation of 7-hydroxy-8-iodo-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (5) (which was obtained by iodination of 1 with iodine and periodic acid in ethanol) to give 7-allyloxy-8-iodo-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (6) and subsequent Claisen migration with *N,N*-dimethylaniline.

The above allylcoumarin 3 on oxidation with $\text{OsO}_4 - \text{KIO}_4$ followed by cyclodehydration with PPA of the intermediate acetaldehyde derivative gave 7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-h][1]benzopyran-5-one (7) (4-propylangelicin). Its structure was established on the basis of elemental analysis, ir spectrum 1720 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1620 and 1610 ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1050, 770 cm^{-1} (furan ring), and ¹H nmr spectrum which showed two doublets *ortho*-coupled (J 9.5 Hz) at δ 7.35 and

7.25 for H-8 and H-9, and one doublet (J 2.5 Hz) at δ 6.88 for H-3 along with other usual signals. However, 3 on trituration with concentrated sulphuric acid gave 2,3-dihydro-2-methyl-7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-h][1]benzopyran-5-one (8) which on dehydrogenation with DDQ yielded 2-methyl-7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-h][1]benzopyran-5-one (9). Its structure was in good agreement with its ir and nmr data (see experimental). Similarly, oxidation of 4 with $\text{OsO}_4 - \text{KIO}_4$ followed by cyclodehydration with PPA yielded a product which was assigned the structure as 5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (10) on the basis of its ir spectrum 1720 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1628 and 1575 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{C}$) and 1105, 785 cm^{-1} (furan ring), and ¹H nmr spectrum which displayed two singlets at δ 7.41 and 7.78 for *para* H-9 and H-4 and a doublet (J_{AB} 2.5 Hz) for H-3. Trituration of 4 with concentrated sulphuric acid gave 2,3-dihydro-2-methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (11). Its dehydrogenation with DDQ afforded 2-methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (12). This structure was in conformity with its ir and nmr data (see experimental).

Similarly, 7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (12) (obtained by Pechman condensation of 1,3-dihydroxy-2-methylbenzene with ethylbutyrylacetate) on allylation with allyl bromide gave 7-allyloxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (14) which on Claisen migration gave only 6-allyl-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (15) (70%). 15 on oxidation with $\text{OsO}_4 - \text{KIO}_4$ and subsequent cyclodehydration afforded 5-propyl-9-methyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (16). Its structure was in good agreement with its spectral data (see experimental). However, trituration of 14 with concentrated sulphuric acid followed by dehydrogenation of the formed 2,9-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (17) with

DDQ yielded 2,9-dimethyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1] benzopyran-7-one (18).

DDQ was used earlier^{1*} for the dehydrogenation of dihydrofuranocoumarins. It has not been used for the dehydrogenation of 2-methyldihydrofuranocoumarins possibly due to the presence of methyl group. However, in the present investigation DDQ has been used successfully for the dehydrogenation of 2-methyldihydrofuranocoumarins 8, 11 and 17.

- 1 $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = H$
- 2 $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OH, -OH = OH_2$
- 3 $R_1 = CH_3, OH = OH_2, R_2 = R_3 = H$
- 4 $R_1 = R_2 = H, R_3 = OH, OH = OH_2$
- 5 $R_1 = I, R_2 = R_3 = H$
- 6 $R_1 = I, R_2 = CH_3, OH = OH_2, R_3 = H$
- 13 $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = R_3 = H$
- 14 $R_1 = CH_3, R_2 = CH_3, OH = OH_2, R_3 = H$
- 15 $R_1 = OH, R_2 = H, R_3 = OH, -OH = OH_2$

- 7 $R = H$
- 9 $R = OH_2$

- 10 $R_1 = R_2 = H$
- 12 $R_1 = H, R_2 = OH_2$
- 16 $R_1 = OH_2, R_2 = H$
- 18 $R_1 = R_2 = CH_3$

8

- 11 $R = H$
- 17 $R = OH_2$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra were determined in KBr with a Perkin-Elmer 598 spectrophotometer. Nmr spectra were run in $CDCl_3$ on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) with TMS as the internal standard. Anhydrous sodium sulphate was used as drying agent.

7-Allyloxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (2) : A solution of 7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (1)¹⁷ (1 g) in dry acetone (75 ml) was refluxed with allyl bromide (0.3 ml) in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g) for 5-6 h. The solution was filtered, solvent distilled off and the residue treated with the crushed ice to give 2 (0.9 g, 78%).

It was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless prisms, m.p. 55-6° (Found : C, 73.7 ; H, 6.5. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.5 ; H, 6.2%) ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.02 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.65 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 4.52 (2H, d, J 5.5 Hz, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.31 (2H, m, $OCH_2-CH=CH_2$), 5.90 (1H, m, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 6.01 (1H, s, H-3), 6.75 (2H, dd, J 9.5 Hz, 2.5 Hz, H-6 and H-8) and 7.40 (1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-5)

Claisen migration of 7-allyloxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one Formation of 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (3) and 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (4) : The above allyloxy coumarin (2) (0.5 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (5 ml) for 6 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured over ice-cold hydrochloric acid. The separated product was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (5%) and the solution filtered. The filtrate on acidification yielded a mixture of two products which were separated by column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the column (i) with benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) gave 8-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (3) and (ii) with benzene afforded 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (4).

3 crystallised from ethanol as shining rectangular plates (0.3 g, 60%), m.p. 112-3° (Found : C, 73.8 ; H, 6.5. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.7 ; H, 6.5%) ; its acetate prepared (Ac_2O/C_6H_5N) melted at 85-6° ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.06 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.60 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.30 (3H, s, $CO-CH_3$), 2.71 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 3.51 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH_2-CH=CH_2$), 5.08 (2H, m, $CH_2-CH=CH_2$), 5.85 (1H, m, $CH_2-CH=CH_2$), 6.22 (1H, s, H-3), 6.98 and 7.49 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

4 crystallised from methanol as colourless plates (0.05 g, 10%), m.p. 140° (Found : C, 73.6 ; H, 6.2. $C_{16}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 73.7 ; H, 6.5%) ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.70 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 3.45 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.05 (2H, m, $CH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.95 (1H, m, $CH_2CH=CH_2$), 6.01, 7.10 and 7.30 (each 1H, each s, H-3, H-8 and H-5, respectively).

7-Hydroxy-8-iodo-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (5) : 7-Hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (1) (2 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of alcohol, and to the solution iodine (1.3 g) and periodic acid (0.56 g) in water were added. The mixture was stirred for 2 h at room temperature and then diluted with water. A solid separated was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol as colourless plates (2.4 g, 76%), m.p. 213-4° (Found : C, 43.5 ; H, 3.3. $C_{16}H_{15}IO_3$ requires C, 43.6 ; H, 3.2%) ; its acetate (Ac_2O/C_6H_5N) melted at 148-9° ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 1.05 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.65 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.32 (3H, s, $CO-CH_3$), 2.69 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 6.20 (1H, s, H-3), 7.05 and 7.55 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

7-Allyloxy-8-iodo-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (6): The above coumarin (5) (2 g) in dry acetone was refluxed with allyl bromide (0.30 ml) in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 for 6 h. Working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 6. It crystallised from methanol as light yellow needles (1.65 g, 75%), m.p. 139-40° (Found: C, 48.4; H, 4.1. $C_{18}H_{18}IO_2$ requires C, 48.5; H, 4.0%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.08 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.65 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.61 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 4.52 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.30 (2H, m, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.85 (1H, m, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 6.01 (1H, s, H-3), 6.75 and 7.55 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

Claisen migration of 6. Formation of (4): The above allyloxy coumarin (6) (0.5 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline for 6 h. Working up of the reaction mixture as above and crystallisation from ethanol gave a product which was identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., ir and nmr) to the coumarin, 6-allyl-7-hydroxy-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (4) obtained above.

7-Propyl-5H-furo[2,3-*h*][1]benzopyran-5-one (7): Allyl coumarin (3) (0.25 g) in ethyl acetate (80 ml) with an equal volume of water was stirred with O_3O_4 (0.06 g). The mixture was shaken for 1.5 h and during the period potassium periodate (2 g) was added in small lots. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h more. The ethyl acetate layer was separated and aqueous solution extracted with more ethyl acetate. The combined ethyl acetate layer was washed well with water, dried and distilled. The residue consisting of acetaldehyde derivative was heated on boiling water bath with polyphosphoric acid (10 ml) for 20 min and then poured over crushed ice. The separated solid was taken up in ether, the ethereal layer washed successively with Na_2CO_3 solution (5%), water, dried and then distilled. The residue on crystallisation from benzene-petroleum ether gave colourless plates of (7) (0.14 g, 6%), m.p. 163-4° (Found: C, 73.2; H, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 73.6; H, 5.2%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 1620 and 1610 (C=C) and 1050, 768 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.01 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.60 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 6.09 (1H, s, H-6), 6.98 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-3), 7.15 and 7.35 (each 1H, d, J 9.5 Hz, H-9 and H-8, respectively) and 7.47 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2).

2,3-Dihydro-2-methyl-7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-*h*][1]benzopyran-5-one (8): Allyl coumarin (3) (0.5 g) was triturated with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) for 15 min. The reaction mixture was poured over crushed ice. The product was filtered, and washed with NaOH solution (5%) and finally with water. 8 was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (0.35 g, 70%), m.p. 97-8° (Found: C, 73.4; H, 6.6. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.6; H, 6.8%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1610, 1575 (C=C), 1100, 1060 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.50

(3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2- CH_3), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.71 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 3.0-3.70 (2H, m, H-3), 5.10 (1H, m, H-1), 6.10 (1H, s, H-6), 6.75 and 7.45 (each 1H, each d, J 2.5 Hz, H-9 and H-8, respectively).

2-Methyl-7-propyl-5H-furo[2,3-*h*][1]benzopyran-5-one (9): Coumarin (8) (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) in anhydrous benzene (10 ml) for 72 h. The solution was filtered, washed successively with Na_2CO_3 solution (10%), water, dried and distilled. The residue, thus obtained was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene-petroleum ether (1:1) gave 9 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as rectangular plates (0.06 g, 60%), m.p. 114-5° (Found: C, 74.3; H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.3; H, 5.7%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 1610, 1598 (C=C), 1098, 775 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.05 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.72 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.48 (3H, s, 2- CH_3), 2.71 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 6.10 and 6.60 (each 1H, each s, H-6 and H-3, respectively), 7.20 and 7.32 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-9 and H-8, respectively).

5-Propyl-7H-furo[3,2-*g*][1]benzopyran-7-one (10): Allyl coumarin (4) (0.25 g) in ethyl acetate (80 ml) containing an equal volume of water was stirred with O_3O_4 (0.06 g). The mixture was shaken for 1.5 h and during the period KIO_4 (2 g) added in small lots. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h more. Working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 10 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as shining rectangular plates (0.14 g, 60%), m.p. 128-9° (Found: C, 73.3; H, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 73.6; H, 5.2%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1625, 1575 (C=C), 1105, 785 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.15 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.80 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.85 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 6.22 (1H, s, H-6), 6.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-3), 7.42 (1H, s, H-9), 7.63 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-2) and 7.80 (1H, s, H-4).

2,3-Dihydro-2-methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-*g*][1]benzopyran-7-one (11): Trituration of 4 (0.5 g) with concentrated sulphuric acid (10 ml) for 15 min and working up of the reaction mixture as above gave a solid which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (0.35 g, 70%), m.p. 115-6° (Found: C, 73.6; H, 5.5. $C_{15}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 73.5; H, 5.2%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1705 (C=O), 1620, 1580 (C=C), 1110 and 1090 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 1.49 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2- CH_3), 1.75 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.69 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_3$), 2.89-3.50 (2H, m, H-3), 5.01 (1H, m, H-2), 6.05, 6.65 and 7.31 (each 1H, each s, H-6, H-9 and H-5, respectively).

2-Methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-*g*][1]benzopyran-7-one (12): Coumarin (11) (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) in anhydrous benzene (10 ml) for 72 h. Working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 12 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (0.06 g, 60%),

m.p. 140° (Found : C, 74.2; H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 74.4; H, 5.7%). ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 1610, 1575 (C=C), 1100, 810 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.09 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.79 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.49 (3H, s, 2- CH_3), 2.79 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 6.27, 6.49, 7.40 and 7.22 (each 1H, each s, H-6, H-8, H-3 and H-5, respectively).

7-Hydroxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (13): A mixture of 1,3-dihydroxy-2-methylbenzene (10 g) and ethyl butyrylacetate (9.2 ml) was cooled (0-5°) in an ice bath and concentrated sulphuric acid (25 ml) was added gradually with shaking. The yellow oil, thus obtained, was kept in refrigerator for 24 h and then poured over crushed ice with constant stirring. The separated solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (15.8 g, 90%), m.p. 165-6° (Found : C, 72.4; H, 5.2. $C_{15}H_{14}O_8$ requires C, 72.2; H, 5.5%); its acetate prepared (Ac_2O/C_6H_5N) melted at 106-7°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.09, (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.75 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.30 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 2.40 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 2.80 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 6.23 (1H, s, H-3), 7.02 and 7.50 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

7-Allyloxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (14): A solution of coumarin (13) (1 g) in dry acetone (75 ml) was refluxed with allyl bromide (0.32 ml) in presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (3.0 g) for 6 h. Working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 14 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as shining prisms (0.9 g, 80%), m.p. 80-81° (Found : C, 75.2; H, 6.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 75.6; H, 6.9%); δ (CDCl₃) 1.01 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.30 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 2.70 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 4.10 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $OCH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.42 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $OCH_2-CH=CH_2$), 5.80 (1H, m, $OCH_2-CH=CH_2$), 6.09 (1H, s, H-3), 6.85 and 7.45 (each 1H, each d, J 9.5 Hz, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (15): Allyloxy coumarin (14) (0.5 g) was refluxed with *N,N*-dimethylaniline (5 ml) for 6 h. Working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 15 which crystallised from ethanol as colourless needles (0.35 g, 70%), m.p. 124-5° (Found : C, 75.8; H, 6.5. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 75.6; H, 6.9%); its acetate prepared (Ac_2O/C_6H_5N) melted at 91-2°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.00 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.65 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.20 (3H, s, CO- CH_3), 2.32 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 2.70 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 3.25 (2H, d, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH=CH_2$), 5.01 (2H, m, $CH_2-CH=CH_2$), 5.80 (1H, m, $CH_2-CH=CH_2$), 6.12 and 7.32 (each 1H, each s, H-3 and H-5, respectively).

9-Methyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (16): Coumarin (15) (0.25 g) in ethyl acetate (80 ml) containing an equal volume of water was stirred with OsO_4 (0.06 g) for 1.5 h and during the period potassium periodate (2 g) added in small lots. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 h more and worked up as above to give 16 which crystallised

from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (0.14 g, 60%), m.p. 133-4° (Found : C, 75.0; H, 6.1. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 74.8; H, 5.9%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1590 (C=C) and 1080, 760 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.50 (3H, s, 8- CH_3), 2.80 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 6.15 (1H, s, H-6), 6.70 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-3) and 7.60 (2H, m, H-2 and H-4).

2,3-Dihydro-2,9-dimethyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (17): 6-Allyl-7-hydroxy-8-methyl-4-propyl-2H-1-benzopyran-2-one (15) (0.5 g) was triturated with concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml) for 15 min and working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 17 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles (0.35 g, 70%), m.p. 140-1° (Found : C, 75.4; H, 6.8. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 75.6; H, 6.9%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 1620, 1580 (C=C) and 1100, 1090 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.50 (3H, d, J 7 Hz, 2- CH_3), 1.65 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.30 (3H, s, 9- CH_3), 2.70 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.90-3.50 (2H, m, H-3), 5.01 (1H, m, H-2), 6.10 and 7.30 (each 1H, each s, H-6 and H-5, respectively).

2,9-Dimethyl-5-propyl-7H-furo[3,2-g][1]benzopyran-7-one (18): A solution of coumarin (17) (0.1 g) was refluxed with DDQ (0.1 g) in anhydrous benzene (10 ml) for 56 h and working up of the reaction mixture as above gave 18 which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless plates (0.06 g, 60%), m.p. 165-6° (Found : C, 72.2; H, 6.3. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8$ requires C, 75.4; H, 6.1%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1710 (C=O), 1610, 1585 (C=C), 1050, 760 cm^{-1} (furan ring); δ (CDCl₃) 1.10 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_3CH_2CH_2$), 1.70 (2H, m, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 2.50 and 2.58 (each 3H, each s, 2- and 9- CH_3), 2.80 (2H, t, J 7 Hz, $CH_2CH_2CH_2$), 6.19, 6.40 and 7.53 (each 1H, each s, H-6, H-3 and H-4, respectively).

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